

10 June 2025

Press release

The CST4ALL project hosted the online “Industry Workshop on the integration of Concentrated Solar Thermal Technologies (CST) with energy storage” on 19 May 2025, bringing together 142 energy sector stakeholders from 29 countries worldwide, including representatives from the European Commission (EC), national authorities, industry, associations, engineering and consultancy firms, research institutions and universities.

The workshop, organised by ESTELA with contributions from all project partners and the support of the European Technology and Innovation Platform on Renewable Heating & Cooling (RHC-ETIP), aimed to explore the industrial potential of CST-energy storage integration concepts.

Dr. Konstantinos Genikomsakis of ESTELA opened the event with welcoming remarks and introduced the CST4ALL project’s activities and workshop’s objectives. He also thanked the participants for contributing their inputs to the completed public opinion survey on Green Deal (GD) challenges & social sciences and humanities (SSH) and gender aspects within the project framework.

On behalf of the EC, Elisabeth Schellmann welcomed the workshop’s focus on the synergies between CST and energy storage and further outlined the goals of the Clean Industrial Deal, the Affordable Energy Action Plan and the adoption of legislation packages under the Net Zero Industry Act (NZIA).

Keynote presentations explored various aspects of CST/CSP integration with energy storage technologies. Diego Caro Pegalajar of ACCIONA Industrial focused on enhancing grid stability, making special reference to the recent blackout in Spain, highlighted lessons learned from a similar incident in Australia and shared insights about current strategies in China. Alberto Crespo Iniesta of ENERGY-NEST presented thermal energy storage solutions for industrial decarbonisation, emphasising the use of heat from renewable sources and/or cheap electricity, and showcased four commercial projects demonstrating different approaches for integrating thermal energy storage, with two of them specifically focused on integration with CST.

During a live poll, participants identified high-temperature industrial process heat, dispatchable electricity generation for grid stability and hybrid systems combining multiple renewable technologies as the most promising applications for CST-storage integration in Europe. They also indicated cost competitiveness as the most critical factor for the wider adoption of CST projects with energy storage in Europe, followed by the demonstration of successful commercial-scale projects.

The roundtable discussion, moderated by Dr. Derek Baker of ODTÜ-GÜNAM Center for Solar Energy Research and Applications, featured a diverse panel of experts from both sectors. They exchanged views on key areas such as industrial maturity and applications, project financing and risk mitigation, regional integration, skills and workforce, market potential and manufacturing facilities, R&I contributions and priorities, as well as synergies and collaboration between the two sectors.

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In the last session, Dr. Peter Heller of DLR, coordinator of the CST4ALL project, summarised the main insights from the workshop. A key takeaway was that CST with integrated energy storage has an essential role to play in Europe's clean energy transition, offering unique advantages in grid stability, 24/7 energy availability, and industrial process heat decarbonisation. With over 50 commercial plants worldwide using molten salt storage, CST with integrated storage is a mature and versatile solution that can be effectively hybridised with other renewable energy technologies, such as solar PV, to reduce energy costs and provide additional value rather than competing with them. Driving the wider adoption of these technologies requires coordinated efforts among industry, academia, and policymakers to advance demonstration projects, develop supportive regulatory frameworks, strengthen workforce capabilities, and implement coordinated communication campaigns to highlight the system value of CST-storage integration for achieving Europe's decarbonisation goals under the Clean Industrial Deal.

This CST4ALL project event was organised with the support of the European Technology and Innovation Platform on Renewable Heating & Cooling (RHC-ETIP).

CST4ALL Coordinator

DLR: Deutsches Zentrum für Luft - und Raumfahrt e.V. (DE)

CST4ALL Partners

CIEMAT: Centro de Investigaciones Energéticas, Medioambientales y Tecnológicas (ES)

ENEA: Agenzia nazionale per le nuove tecnologie, l'energia e lo sviluppo economico sostenibile (IT)

ESTELA: European Solar Thermal Electricity Association (BE)

GUNAM: Center for Solar Energy Research and Applications (TR)

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The CST4ALL project is committed to catalysing an array of hybridisation and cooperation initiatives at the interface between CST and other renewable energy technologies targeting the electricity, heat, and fuels sectors.

To stay up-to-date on CST4ALL's activities and opportunities, follow the project on:

- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/cst4all/>
- X (formerly Twitter): <https://twitter.com/Cst4All>
- Website: <https://cst4all.eu/en/>

You can also sign-up for the **CST4ALL Newsletter** to receive updates on other project events and outputs through the following link: <https://cst4all.eu/en/4169-contact-connect>.

